

treatments and weed control methods, including a weed-free and weedy check, were main plot treatments.

Seedlings were transplanted in lines at 20- × 20- cm spacing in a field fertilized with 5 t farmyard manure/ha. Hand and rotary weeding were performed once at 35 d after transplanting (DT), or twice at 21 and 40 DT. Butachlor granules were broadcast 2 DT at 2 kg ai/ha with or without one hand or rotary weeding at 35 DT. Weeding costs were estimated on the basis of current labor charges, cost of herbicide, and time taken to apply it.

A minimum 10 m² from the center of each plot was harvested to determine grain yield. Weed control methods were compared to local farmer practice (one hand weeding) by calculating return above variable cost (RAVC) and marginal benefit-to-cost ratio (MBCR).

Principal weed species were *Cyperus rotundus* and *Fimbristylis miliacea*. Other species found were *Cyperus* spp., *Cynodon dactylon*, *Echinochloa* spp. and *Paspalum distichum*. All weed control treatments gave a significantly higher yield than the weedy check (see table). Response of the varieties to the treatments was broadly similar. The highest yields, comparable to that of the weed-free check, came from the butachlor treatments and were not significantly different from yields with one or two hand or rotary weeding. There was no yield advantage in supplementing butachlor with hand or rotary weeding. A single rotary weeding 35 DT appeared to be more effective than a single hand weeding, and was statistically comparable to 2 rotary weeding.

Compared with farmer practice (one hand weeding), rotary weeding treatments had substantial RAVC, reflecting both reduced costs and increased benefits. But unlike the alternative weed control treatments, which can be applied in randomly planted rice (the common practice in Wangdiphodrang), rotary weeding requires line planting. That may entail increased costs if more planting time is needed.

Of the remaining treatments, a second hand weeding gave some economic advantage over farmer practice, but a single application of butachlor was outstanding economically.

Both butachlor and rotary weeding appear to be promising labor-saving weed control methods in rice under Bhutanese conditions. □

Weeds disseminated with rice seedlings

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In Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines, we observed that weed seedlings and weed seeds were disseminated with rice seedlings during transplanting. An average of 51 weed seedlings were counted in each of 450 rice seedling bundles, which contained an average 684 rice seedlings. Farmers did not separate out the weed seedlings before transplanting.

Fourteen species belonging to five families were transplanted with the rice seedlings: the most common were

Echinochloa glabrescens and *Paspalum distichum* (see table). These weeds are highly competitive with rice and difficult to control.

An average 427 weed seeds were found attached to the roots of rice seedlings in each of 300 bundles examined. Twenty weed species, predominantly *Cyperus difformis*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Rotala catholica*, and *Lindernia antipoda*, which were disseminated in this manner, added to the weed seed reserves in the soil. Depending on dormancy and viability, they will be a source of infestation, not only in the crop in which they were disseminated but also in future crops. □

Weeds disseminated with rice seedlings in farmers fields, Guimba, Nueva Ecija, Philippines.

Weed species	Family	Seedlings (no.)	Seeds (no.)
<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	Lythraceae	—	10.5
<i>Ammannia octandra</i> L. f.	Lythraceae	—	16.2
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	Cyperaceae	5.7	104.0
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	Cyperaceae	0.1	3.3
<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	1.1	1.8
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Poaceae	1.2	—
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	Poaceae	3.1	2.8
<i>Echinochloa glabrescens</i> Munro ex Hook. f.	Poaceae	10.9	9.3
<i>Echinochloa oryzoides</i> (Ard.) Fritsch.	Poaceae	5.0	—
<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Asteraceae	0.1	3.3
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	Cyperaceae	4.4	86.5
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	Poaceae	0.9	—
<i>Lindernia antipoda</i> (L.) Alston	Scrophulariaceae	0.1	65.7
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	Onagraceae	—	2.8
<i>Ludwigia perennis</i> L.	Onagraceae	—	6.7
<i>Melochia concatenata</i> L.	Sterculiaceae	—	0.2
<i>Monochoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl	Pontederiaceae	0.3	25.2
<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	Poaceae	13.6	0.8
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	Poaceae	—	0.3
<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schum. & Thonn.	Euphorbiaceae	—	0.3
<i>Rotala catholica</i> (Cham. & Schlecht.) B. van Leeuwen	Lythraceae	—	67.5
<i>Scirpus supinus</i> L.	Cyperaceae	4.8	18.7
<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> L.	Aizoaceae	—	1.5

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Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Effect of seedling root dip and main field treatment on *Hirschmanniella mucronata* and rice yield

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A microplot field trial at the OUAT Central Research Station in 1985 kharif investigated suitable control measures for the rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella mucronata*. Jaya seedlings of age 28 d were raised in an untreated nursery with an initial average nematode population of 105/200 cm³

soil. The main experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with 7 treatments (subplot size 4 m²), each replicated 5 times: roots dipped for 6 h in normal water (T₁ = control) or in 0.1% aqueous solutions of isofenphos (T₂), diazinon (T₃), BPMC (T₄), monocrotophos (T₅), oncol (T₆), or carbofuran (T₇). The recommended dose of NPK fertilizer was applied. The treated seedlings were transplanted at a spacing of 20 × 15 cm. Carbofuran was broadcast at 1 kg ai/ha at 50 d after transplanting.

The *H. mucronata* population before transplanting ranged from 131 to

136/200 cm³ soil, but at harvest it was maximum in the control and minimal in T₄ (see table), indicating poor population buildup with BPMC. T₇ and T₄ plots had low nematode populations/gram of root, and supported a greater number of flowering tillers and taller plants at harvest than the other treatments. T₇ had maximum grain harvest, followed by T₂ and T₄, which did not differ significantly. Isofenphos, BPMC, and carbofuran gave yield increases of 21-23% over control, indicating their superiority to the other treatments. □

Effect of seedling root dip and main field treatment on *H. mucronata* and rice yield.^a OUAT, Orissa, India, 1985 kharif.

Treatment ^a	Nematodes (no.)			Flowering tillers (no.)	Plant height (cm)	Yield		Increase (%) over control
	Per 200 cm ³ soil		Per g root			g/4 m ²	t/ha	
	Before planting	Ai harvest						
T ₁	132	395	7.8	4.2	82.0	842	2.1	
T ₂	136	212	4.8	5.0	93.0	1032	2.6	23
T ₃	136	206	5.8	5.0	93.4	960	2.4	14
T ₄	131	182	4.6	5.4	95.8	1017	2.5	21
T ₅	132	199	6.0	5.2	94.4	860	2.2	2
T ₆	134	224	5.6	5.2	94.4	986	2.5	17
T ₇	133	199	4.4	5.6	99.4	1037	2.6	23
CD (0.05)	ns	21	0.8	ns	5.0	52		

^a Mean of 5 replications.

Soil and Crop Management

Response to K application of rice in iron-rich valley soils

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We studied the effect of applied K on Fe toxicity and associated nutritional disorders under conditions of shallow water table in wetland rice soil rich in Fe

at Farm Barapani, East Khasi Hills, Meghalaya (25.7 °N, 91.9 °E). The soil was sandy loam, pH 5.05, 1.55% organic C, Bray's P₁ 6 mg/kg, 55 mg exchangeable K/kg, and 1.97% active Fe.

The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with eight K treatments (muriate of potash) replicated four times. A basal dose of 80 kg N as urea and 40 kg P as single

superphosphate/ ha were applied. Rice variety Ngoba was transplanted in Jun 1985 (monsoon season). Plant samples taken at 35 and 70 d after transplanting (DT) and total K, P, and Fe contents of grain and straw yield samples were estimated using standard procedures.

Where no K was applied, at 50 DT emerging leaves were erect and narrow. Early symptoms of Fe toxicity were yellowing followed by reddish brown